

DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY-PROFESSIONAL VALUES BY FORMING THE IDEA OF THE PROSPERITY OF THE MOTHERLAND IN FUTURE OFFICERS

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Annotation. The article emphasizes the importance of introducing new methods, means, forms, their management and control in the development of military professional values by forming the idea of national development among cadets. Undoubtedly, an integrated approach to this, especially in the process of working outside the classroom, that is, on the basis of family and social cooperation, glorifying the student's profession, forming a spirit of loyalty to the chosen profession, will be important. fruits.

Keywords and concepts: personal development, society, motherland, development of professional values, glorification of the profession, formation of the spirit of loyalty to the chosen profession.

From the first days of the third renaissance, in the prosperity, prosperity and increase in power of new Uzbekistan, it is important to train mature officers in all respects in the process of military training. The development of military-professional values by forming the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in future officers is one of the most relevant and important pedagogical - psychological problems today.

The formation of the idea of the prosperity of the motherland is associated with raising the morale of the individual, society to a high level, the importance of which is extremely important. The person who embodies the idea of the prosperity of the motherland meets the spiritual requirements of society, his own professional values, strengthens it. The purpose of forming the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in future officers is not only limited to strengthening the prospects and prospects of our society, but also contributes to the development of a professional culture based on national and universal values. In the development of professional values by forming the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in future officers, it is important to implement, control and control innovative methods, tools, forms. An integrated approach to this, of course, pays off, especially in the process of lesson, educational work beyond the audience, at the same time glorifying the military profession in the person of a cadet on the basis of family, neighborhood cooperation, forming a spirit of loyalty to the chosen profession.

Today, the content of Education has been radically reformed. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan – Supreme Commander - in – chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his address to the Supreme Assembly, " it is clear to all that both the cornerstone of development and the power that makes the country powerful and the nation great are science, education and education. Tomorrow, the lightness of our Motherland is closely related, first of all, to the educational system and the upbringing we give our children....If we

strive, work hard, it is best to master any high finish. We are the people of the "bright dark" when it comes to enlightenment. Striving for science is in our blood, in today's language, in our gene.

"The greatest wealth is intelligence and science, the greatest inheritance is good upbringing, and the greatest poverty is ignorance," they emphasize.

Upbringing means, first of all, the preparation of the younger generation for the future life and for some profession. Upbringing is an organized pedagogical process for the purposeful formation of an individual, providing an opportunity to regularly and systematically influence the person of upbringing-Chi. When we talk about the upbringing process, this training is carried out through knowledge, skills and qualifications with specially organized educational activities. At this point, in the process of upbringing, which forms professional abilities, the mind of the educator is formed, emotions are developed, behavioral habits are formed that are necessary for social life and serve social ties.

The development of today's education requires that the teacher work on himself, be creative, improve the knowledge, skills and skills of students.

Therefore, every coach engaged in the education of young people in the educational process should be well aware of the spiritual heritage of our traditions, national values, great thinkers and apply them to classes, paying attention to the fact that they enjoy the cups of folk humanism, universal values in order to make students a harmonious person.

In the process of upbringing, it is extremely important to increase the exactingness of cadets in relation to the profession of their choice, to organize their activities pedagogically correctly through a Real assessment of the situation when educating them so that they are not distracted from various problems, able to chase the product of Labor. In the process of training, an educator should organize his classes as a result of helping his creative maturity, relying on the advanced forces in the minds of future officers based on educational methods that he can approach with various elements, such as patriotism, perseverance, patience and perseverance.

The relationship between the teacher and the cadet should encourage the enjoyment of the achievements, a responsible approach to educational activities and the establishment of creative activities in mutual cooperation. This gives rise to the "bridge", the means of interaction necessary for the organization of pedagogical influence.

In its content, such ideas as national and universal values, prosperity of the motherland, Motherland, nationality, goodness, increasing the dignity of the profession occupy a deep place. In particular, the issue of instilling affection for the military profession in relation to the absorption of basic concepts and principles of the idea of national independence into the hearts of future officers is an important problem of modern education and upbringing. Because the main link of the idea of the prosperity of the motherland leads the people towards high development by improving the human factor and its professional skills, developing economic, legal, political, spiritual directions in each area.

It should be noted that educational institutions –the Timurbek School, higher military educational institutions-are actively involved in the systematic formation of professional values. State educational standards of Higher Education also indicate that the general qualification requirements for the training of graduates should "be able to express and scientifically substantiate their opinion on the issues of knowledge of the history of the motherland, spiritual, national and Universal, professional values, have an active professional

point of view based on the idea of national independence". Therefore, today, along with improving the activities of Higher Military Education, the humanization of education, the formation of high morale, culture and thinking in education recipients are the priorities of state policy.

Therefore, the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications in cadets receiving education in higher military educational institutions to have a common and professional culture, to be able to act independently in a creative and socially active, socio-political profession, to develop the prosperity of the Motherland is one of the main tasks of the higher military educational institution.

Of course, in the implementation of these tasks, it is important to form professional skills in cadets of a higher military educational institution. Because the formation of the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in Cadets is a mechanism for the systematic advancement of military-professional knowledge, skills that must be acquired, as well as being a key factor in the development of society. This is the first.

Secondly, the vision of the military profession, which is necessary to be occupied by organizing the education of cadets of higher military educational institutions on the basis of the idea of the prosperity of the motherland, expands, and also emerges as an important condition for the development of the spirituality of society, the stability of the country. Today, the cadet does not develop the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in the minds of tomorrow's officer, it is impossible to master the desired military profession in society or achieve high progress. Therefore, the formation of the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in Cadets is important in improving their professional knowledge. Because every young man who is educated in this mask not only has a field specialty, but also matures physically and spiritually. Actively participates in the life of our society. With its spirituality, culture, it works for a free and prosperous homeland, which is the main path of development of Uzbekistan.

Of course, in the implementation of such colossal tasks, cadets must form the idea of the prosperity of the motherland, develop their morale through the military profession, its value and essence, and be educated in the spirit of loyalty to the idea of national independence. Understanding the national identity, restoring our national values, enriching them with the achievements of Science and development, knowing the history, culture of our motherland, fostering loyalty to our sacred religion also increases the competitiveness of young officer personnel.

As a result of the implementation of these tasks, such qualities as new thinking, National thinking, national ideologies, spiritual-moral, love of the profession are matured in the minds of future officers. Choosing a profession and seeing the chosen profession as a value does not appear at once. It goes through dynamic stages such as emergence, content finding, development and consolidation.

The formation of the idea of the prosperity of the motherland through the profession of his choice in future officers is one of the pressing problems and forms the basis of the development of society. In some places, problems with changing the profession may arise among cadets even after passing certain stages. That is why it is socially useful to give future officers knowledge about the idea of the prosperity of the motherland. The formation of skills and competencies of productive work is considered extremely important in the future in the content of their chosen profession.

An analysis of the scientific literature has shown that since the values of this profession are not constantly developed, the problem cannot find the desired solution. In the years of independence on the problem of the absolute development of the values of this profession, several experiments have been carried out, scientific-methodological, popular science literature, manuals are being published.

In the minds of today's youth, the formation of new thinking, National thinking, national ideologies, spiritual and moral qualities, national pride are considered the main criteria in upbringing. This should be understood correctly by each parent in the upbringing of a child. Therefore, we should not forget that it is an urgent issue to direct the career of militarism through the formation of the idea of the prosperity of the Motherland, which is extremely important in the life of our society, our state, determines the tomorrow, our future of all of us.

It is important to educate dedicated officers for the prosperity of the motherland and the nation, to educate intelligent, strong-willed, confident idol with moral and spiritual, physical training, to cultivate young military personnel who strive to learn the experience of developed countries, have a strong sense of Homeland in their hearts, to structure a sense of patriotism in them, to understand and, it is also an impetus for the maturation of skilled professionals who can bring their skills to life.

Published in the years of independence J.Tulenov's "philosophy of values", o.Musurmonova's "formation of the spiritual culture of students", B.Kasimov, U.The dolimovs "'lessons of enlightenment", a.In such scientific and philosophical treatises and works as "spirituality, value and artistry", such issues as the past situation of spiritual and moral and professional values, their restoration thanks to independence, the role of spirituality in human life, the development of a sense of love for an independent Motherland, nation are widely covered pedagogically and psychologically.

By forming the idea of the prosperity of the motherland, we consider the following factors important in the development of military-professional values:

- regular increase in professional knowledge by strengthening the economic power of the state, Freedom of economic activity, modernization of the economy on the basis of advanced technologies;
- bleaching professional skills by increasing the spiritual wealth of the people, its intellectual potential and professionalism;
- to increase the affection for their profession through the comprehensive and full use of the creative abilities of the people;
- to prevent and neutralize external and internal threats to peace, stability and security in the region, to strengthen mutual cooperation and practical cooperation with all countries of Central Asia in combating extremism, terrorism, organized and cross-border crime;
- assist in global efforts not to distribute weapons of mass destruction;
- prevention and end of manifestations of extremism and international terrorism;
- to combat extremism, terrorism and other forms of anti-terrorism that threaten national security in the military sphere;
- elimination of the consequences of emergency situations;
- the cultivation of individuals with a culture of a profession of mature potential in the form of raising spiritually rich, intellectual and highly civilized, morally and physically healthy young people.

Today, improving the quality efficiency of military education is considered one of the most pressing issues.

The globalization of military education and training, the introduction of innovative technologies, at the same time a large-scale flow of information makes it necessary to carry out intensive activities in the development of professional values in future officers, not only regularly updating and improving the content of military education.

Implementation of state policy in the field of education, improvement of the educational process on the basis of unified state requirements in the training of military personnel, provision of educational literature, implementation of the task of continuous methodological service to young military personnel is one of the important and urgent tasks.

Today, it is not enough for us to educate our youth as individuals with a perfect, harmonious, broad worldview in all respects, creative thinking, intellectual potential, but to help them mature even in the direction of their chosen field. Training as knowledgeable, spiritually matured, ideologically mature military in the development of professional values by forming the idea of the prosperity of the motherland in today's officers who are real brave sons of our country is one of the responsible tasks of educators-educators and parents of the present time.

Cultural heritage and the development of high artistic, national traditions, its use, the introduction of methods of creative practice provide the basis for the upbringing of every cadet who is directed to the profession, especially in the form of diligence, endurance, perseverance in them, the study of philosophical, psychological aspects of the profession of his choice in a political-ideological and aesthetic spirit for

In this case, the cadet who is forming a professional skill should pay special attention to the following:

- To be prepared for complex measures to bring the armed forces to a high level of combat;
- study of a scientifically sound system of decisions to be made in the field of development of Military Science and ensuring military security;
- To express their opinion on the changes in the manifestations of threats to national security in the military sphere, the conditions of the military-political situation, the nature of modern military conflicts, the tasks and directions of the development of the state military organization;
- knowledge of professional art, study and evaluation of artistic, scientific works;
- increase the abilities of traceability and creativity;
- strengthening interest in professional art;
- such as creativity and worldview formation.

Today's rapidly changing economic, social and spiritual life the formation of the worldview of future officers assumes the implementation of professional skills saturated with various modern values into life and the widespread use of the latest techniques in this regard. The more solid the knowledge, the more the worldview, intellectual potential of the cadet develops and matures. Currently, the level of informational, informational literacy required for future officers ' careers of their choice is an important condition for improving educational effectiveness. In accordance with the requirements of the state placed before the system of Higher Military Education, which is the highest branch of the system of continuing education, these educational institutions are able to improve the efficiency of the educational process, to

bring to maturity a competent person who feels his duty and responsibility to the state, society and family, in a word, it is intended to carry out such important tasks as instilling in the mind and soul of the "new generation of military personnel" the idea of national independence.

References:

1. Асқарова Ў. Меҳрибонлик уйлари ўсмирларида миллий ғурурни тарбиялашнинг педагогик хусусиятлари. // Педагогика фанлари номзоди илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. – Т., 2001.
2. Аминов Б., Расулов Т. Ватан юракдаги жавоҳир. – Т.: «Ўқитувчи», 2001.
3. Атаджанова Ш. Оилада ўспирин-ёшларни ватанпарварлик руҳида тарбиялашда миллий қадриятлардан фойдаланишнинг педагогик асослари. // Педагогика фанлари номзоди илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. – Т., 2001.
4. Аҳмедов Б. Тарихдан сабоқлар. – Т.: «Ўқитувчи», 1994.
5. Абдуллаев А. Маънавият ва иқтисод, тафаккур. – Т.: «Маънавият», 1999.
6. Иномова М. Оилада болаларни маънавий-ахлоқий тарбиялашда миллий қадриятлардан фойдаланишнинг педагогик асослари (мустақил ҳаёт бўсағасидаги ёшлар). // Педагогика фанлари доктори илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. – Т., 1998.